

A OPEN SCIENCE SURVEY QUESTIONS

ID	Questions
Q1	Graduate Program Center
Q2	Have you heard about Open Science?
Q3	Open Science covers a wide range of different practices. Which are you aware of and/or use?
Q4	How do you assess your overall experience with Open Science practices?
Q5	In your opinion who should Open Science be open to?
Q6	With regard to the concept of Open Science, have you encountered any obstacles (for example, access and reuse of knowledge, data, licenses) to your daily work? If so, could you detail? Otherwise, please answer "No".
Q7	Do you know or have you used any tool that supports Open Science? If so, please provide the name of the tool and, if possible, your access URL. Otherwise, please answer "No".
Q8	When designing an experiment or publishing research results, how much effort (what effort and average number of hours) do you make to see if your inputs or outputs can be reused or shared? Please specify in more detail.
Q9.1	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Diversity: Incorporation of under-represented groups in science (sex, races, cultures, etc.)]
Q9.2	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Efficiency: Sharing data, procedures and / or to optimize science]
Q9.3	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Equity: access to all scientific results, methods, software, etc., regardless of economic or institutional capacity]
Q9.4	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Ethics: Open Science is aligned with integrity research principles]
Q9.5	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Justice: Science is often funded by society, so all research results must be available to society]
Q9.6	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Impact: To overcome traditional metrics for scientific impact: larger audience, greater involvement, etc.]
Q9.7	In your opinion what is the reason for Open Science to be opened? [Rigor: Open access, Open Data and / or Open replicability makes science easier]
Q10.1	In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Not a priority now: There are currently higher priorities in the scientific community]
Q10.2	In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Lack of public and understanding: Society cannot make decisions or have useful input without an understanding of the process]
Q10.3	In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [The public is not ready now: Society is not ready for participation (lack of skills, tools, etc.)]
Q10.4	In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Low quality: Because it is releasing publications before peer reviews, the veracity of the papers will be difficult to assess for each individual. Quality is not guaranteed]

- Q10.5 In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Potential danger of misuse: Open Science can interfere with research integrity. It could also facilitate the misuse of search results (for example, biological weapons)]
- Q10.6 In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Lack of incentives: Open data / publication is contrary to "meritocracy" and individual effort and is not rewarded by traditional metrics]
- Q10.7 In your opinion why shouldn't Open Science be opened? [Injustice: If a research group generates knowledge with its own resources. it could be unfair if others used it to obtain economic benefits for themselves]
- Q11 Imagine that the institution where you work adopts Open Science practices. In your opinion, what are the most important barriers you would face?
- Q12 Do you already participate in any Open Science activity / action (if so, what type)? Otherwise, please answer "No".
- Q13 Have you received any training from your institution regarding Open Science (if so, what type)? Otherwise, please answer "No".
- Q14 Do you receive support or incentives from your institution related to Open Science? [Written guidelines: (web page / brochure / videos), policies, recommendations]
- Q15 Do you receive support or incentives from your institution related to Open Science? [Technical infrastructure: (models, software, storage, databases, publication and / or data repositories, etc.)]
- Q16.1 Do you receive support or incentives from your institution related to Open Science? [Specialized support: (experts on different aspects of Open Science, research data committees, courses, workshops, etc.)]
- Q16.2 Do you receive support or incentives from your institution related to Open Science? [Financial support and rewards]
- Q16.3 Do you receive support or incentives from your institution related to Open Science? [Career prospects and recognition]
- Q17 Creative Commons are public licenses that allow free distribution of a copyrighted work. Have you used / use some of the ones listed below in your research?
- Q18 In your opinion, how do you see sharing / reusing data for everyone to use and publish, without restrictions on copyrights and patents or other control mechanisms. Do you agree with the idea or do you think there should be some restrictions?
- Q19 What is your opinion on data repositories? Currently, they meet the researcher's needs with access to the data they need on the research subject and also make the data citable through a DOI. Examples of repositories are Zenodo and FigShare.
- Q20 Overall, if you had to summarize your view on Open Science, what would you have to say?
- Q21 Would you as a researcher adopt Open Science for your research and development environment? If so, for what type of production? Otherwise, please answer "No".
- Q22 Do you have any comments, suggestions or anything else to say about the survey and the topic covered?
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